

Understanding Of Disaster Risk Management In Madagascar

Rakotoarimanana Zy Misa Harivelo^{1*}, Rakotoarimanana Zy Harifidy², Rakotovao Soatsitohaina Ravaonjalitera³

¹ Department of Disaster Management, Postgraduate School, Universitas Airlangga, Indonesia

² Engineering and Agricultural Sciences, Integrated Graduated School of Medicine, University of Yamanashi, Japan

³ Department of Mines, Ecole Supérieure Polytechnique, Université d'Antananarivo, Madagascar

Accepted October 03,2021

Published October 11,2021

*Corresponding Author:
Rakotoarimanana Zy Misa
Harivelo

DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5562328>

Pages: 01-10

Funding: None

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):
Zy Misa, H. R., Zy Harifidy, R., &
Soatsitohaina, R. R., (2021).
Understanding Of Disaster Risk
Management In Madagascar.
*North American Academic
Research*, 4(10), 01-10. doi:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5562328>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

drought periods; increased variability of the rainfall regime; intensification of cyclones; floods associated with cyclonic disturbances [3]. In urban communities, intense heavy rainfall events and cyclones are expected to exacerbate flood risk. In coastal areas, storm surges from the increasing cyclone intensity combined with sea level rise will put urban infrastructure at high risk of inundation and coastal erosion [4]. Rapidly growing cities and rural towns are exposed to flooding, storms, drought and heat stress that impact human health and safety, economic activities, and urban infrastructure and services.

ABSTRACT

Madagascar is one of the African countries most severely affected by climate change impacts and extreme weather events. Natural disasters pose a great challenge in Madagascar in terms of frequency and damage. With a greater capacity of the individual, community and environment to face the disasters, the impact of a hazard would be significantly reduced. The overall objective of this article is to gain insights about the natural hazards and their trends in Madagascar. This article also examines the best practices and problems militating against effective disaster management in the country.

Keywords: DISASTER MANAGEMENT, HAZARDS, MADAGASCAR, PREPAREDNESS

Introduction

Located in Southwestern Indian Ocean basin, just off the south-eastern edge of the African continent, Madagascar is the fourth largest island in the world. Due to its diverse landscape, Madagascar is exposed to a variety of weather and climate phenomena [1]. One-quarter of Madagascar's population approximately five million people are estimated to be vulnerable to natural disasters, including tropical cyclones, storm surges, floods, droughts, earthquakes and locust invasions [2]. Climate change impacts are severe in the country during the last two decades: extended

Disaster management is an important policy issue because monetary losses from natural disasters are reaching catastrophic proportions and are expected to increase. If a country ignores disaster risk and allows risk to accumulate, it is in effect undermining its own future potential for social and economic development. However, if a country invests in disaster risk reduction, over time it can reduce the potential losses it faces, thus freeing up critical resources for development [5].

The basis of this article is to provide some information about the natural hazards and their trends in Madagascar. This article also examines the best practices and problems militating against effective disaster management in the country.

Materials and methods

1. Common disasters in Madagascar

1.1. Cyclone

Madagascar's location puts the country in a first position of nation most exposed to cyclone in the African continent and ranked among the ten countries most vulnerable to extreme weather events in the world [6]. Every year, the country is a potential target of tropical cyclones that form in the South West Indian Ocean basin [7]. More than 60% of the tropical cyclones that form in the basin directly or indirectly affect Madagascar. Tropical cyclones constitute a constant threat to the safety and well-being of the population. Madagascar ranked among the top 10 countries with the highest index (index 6) of the risk of mortality associated with the cyclone, a level of risk similar to India and Haiti. According to the World Bank, thirty to one hundred deaths associated with cyclones per year are recorded in Madagascar [8]. With a mortality risk index linked to the capacity of each country to respond to a cyclone event among the highest in the world, Madagascar is very vulnerable [9],[10]. On average, 03 cyclones with intensity of 132 km / h per year cross Madagascar, generally affecting two thirds of the country. The cyclone season in Madagascar took place from November to April, the most active period has been between mid-December and mid-March and can vary enormously in intensity, speed and destructive power. Between 2009 and 2018, Madagascar was hit by 27 cyclones and tropical storms. The East, North-East, West and Southwest coasts are the most exposed to tropical cyclone. The most powerful cyclones originate from North-west and North-east of the island. Recent research suggests that while the frequency of cyclones will decrease along this part of the Southern Indian Ocean, their intensity is projected to increase, and could severely impact the country's GDP (leading to a 38% decline in the balance of payments) [8]. Moreover, the National Department of Meteorology, during the study on climate change in Madagascar predicts around the year 2055, a general increase in precipitation from January to April, and an increase in the frequency of intense cyclones around 2100.

1.2. Drought

Droughts seriously threaten livelihoods, causing water shortages and crop losses, leading to food insecurity and malnutrition. In the three sub-arid regions of the south of the island are the hottest and driest parts of the

island (Androy, Anosy and Atsimo-Andrefana), frequently hit by a long period of rainfall deficit. Those regions receive on average only about 500 mm of precipitation and during severe drought, the annual precipitation does not even reach 300 mm [11]. The drought season in the Southern region is generally from December to March, although the first signs often appear as early as October. The agricultural production relies heavily on the supply of rain which has been decreasing. More than half of the labor force is employed in agriculture, but this has not guaranteed food security. According to Integrated Phase Classification (IPC) during the period (January to April 2021), 1.35 million people are estimated to be facing high levels of acute food insecurity (IPC Phase 3 or above). That includes 282,000 people expected to be in Emergency (IPC Phase 4) and 1.067 million in Crisis (IPC Phase 3). Additionally, 135,476 children are likely to suffer from acute malnutrition in the ten analyzed districts, including 27,137 severe cases.

1.3. Earthquake

Madagascar experiences local seismic activity related to its slow separation from the African continent and, as a result has more local earthquakes. The earthquake hazard is classified as low in Madagascar, there is a 2% chance of potentially damaging earthquake shaking in the next 50 years [12]. The areas with the highest risks are Antananarivo, Mahajanga, Toliary, along with coastal areas in the Northwest of Antsiranana [13]. The strongest earthquakes recorded in Madagascar do not exceed magnitude 6.0. These are the earthquake of 29 March 1943 with magnitude $M_s = 6.0$ and the earthquake of 09 November 1955 with intensity of VII MM (Modified Mercalli intensity).

1.4. Epidemic

In the last five years, the country experienced two major epidemics in two successive years: pneumonic plague in 2017 and measles in 2018. The loss of human life has been enormous, reaching around 1,400 deaths. The plague outbreak has affected the country's economy, especially the tourism and transport sectors. The country has faced several types of epidemics: COVID-19 in 22 regions, malaria in the southern regions, dengue in the central west.

- Coronavirus

After the World Health Organization (WHO) declared COVID-19 a global pandemic, Madagascar declared a state of emergency and reported its three first cases on 20 March 2020. For Madagascar, like many other countries, there remains social distancing including local and national lockdowns of populations to control the COVID-19 pandemic. However, social distancing measures can lead the vulnerable groups at the brink of hunger and starvation, which a worse threat than the pandemic itself. The implementation of confinement in developing countries is far to be achieved due to poverty and to the lack of education of the majority of the population [14]. Given the structural fragility of the country's health system and the existence of aggravating factors such as very precarious water, hygiene and sanitation conditions, COVID-19 was able to spread rapidly

in Madagascar [15]. The COVID-19 epidemic could become the leading public health problem in Madagascar, causing nearly twice as many deaths as are attributed to diarrheal disease [16]. During the COVID-19 emergency response on June 2020, 1.6 million people were reached with critical WASH supplies. Over 4 million people were reached with COVID-19 risk communication and community engagement [17]. On 09th April 2021, a total of 26 127 positive cases with 469 deaths had been recorded [18]. The impact of the pandemic will cast a long shadow on economic and social prospects and could be compounded by other shocks, including droughts and other climatic events affecting already vulnerable populations [19].

1.5. Flood

The heavy rains brought by cyclones, the filling of surface or alluvial aquifers during prolonged rains, the repetition of strong rainy seasons, the difficulties of infiltration into the soil due to geological and pedological specificities and the siltation of certain rivers favor flooding in some parts of the country [20]. Urban cities such as Antananarivo, Tulear, Maroantsetra and Tsihombe are often victims of the flood risk. During the post-cyclonic period, the heavy rains and cyclone induced flooding weaken the population's resilience and plunge them into indescribable poverty as 80 % of Madagascar's population is involved in agriculture. The destruction of crops, agricultural areas and the inaccessibility of road infrastructure led to the risk of food insecurity. Transport infrastructures are the first to be disrupted by flooding. Roads are destroyed and the national roads are often cut which affect the development of the country's economy. In addition, cyclones and floods regularly contaminate urban wells and increase the risk of water-borne diseases [4].

1.6. Landslide

Landslide is classified as high in the capital city Antananarivo and Eastern part of Madagascar. It occurred particularly during cyclonic period or during the famous “Zone de Convergence Inter-Tropical” (ZCIT) passage in the western part of the Indian Ocean. The lack of a proper urban planning, rainfall patterns, terrain slope, geology, soil and land cover make those areas particularly prone to landslide. Landslides and mass movements in Madagascar cause a few fatalities per year. They pose threats to settlements and structures, and often result in catastrophic damage to roads, pipelines, buildings and agricultural lands [21].

2. Losses due to disasters

Disasters had economic, social and health impacts. The economic impacts were the most important, as a disruption of all livelihoods had economic implications in Madagascar.

The Table 1 bellow presented the effects of disasters including drought, floods, extreme weather, cyclone and epidemic in Madagascar from 1968 - 2021.

Table 1: Natural Hazard Effects in Madagascar [22]

Natural Disasters from 1968 - 2021	
No. of events:	89
No. of people killed:	5154
Average killed per year:	75
No. of people affected:	18577813
Average affected per year:	269244
No. of people homeless	1119607
Average homeless per year:	74640
No. of people injured	112432
Average injured per year:	1263
Economic Damage (\$ X 1,000):	2346801
Economic Damage per year (\$ X 1,000):	80924

Table 2: Top 10 natural disasters in terms of killed, number affected and economic damages [22]

Disaster type	Date	No Killed	Disaster type	Date	No Affected	Disaster type	Date	Damage US \$
Epidemic	Mar 1999	860	Tropical cyclone	Feb 1972	2510056	Tropical cyclone	Feb 1977	350000
Epidemic	Jul 2002	671	Insect infestation	Oct 2010	2300000	Tropical cyclone	Dec 1981	250000
Tropical cyclone	Mar 2004	363	Drought	Apr 2018	1260000	Tropical cyclone	Mar 1982	250000
Tropical cyclone	Jan 1994	207	Drought	Jan 2016	1140000	Tropical cyclone	Apr 1984	250000
Drought	Apr 1988	200	Drought	1981	1000000	Tropical cyclone	Mar 2004	250000
Tropical cyclone	Jan 1994	200	Tropical cyclone	Mar 2004	988139	Tropical cyclone	Mar 2007	240000
Tropical cyclone	Feb 1997	140	Drought	Apr 1988	950000	Tropical cyclone	Mar 1986	150000
Epidemic	Dec 1999	130	Tropical cyclone	Feb 2000	736937	Flood	Jan 2003	150000
Tropical cyclone	Mar 2010	121	Drought	Jan 2020	725620	Tropical cyclone	Feb 2012	100000

Tropical cyclone	Dec 1981	120	Drought	2008	720000	Tropical cyclone	Feb 2008	60000
------------------	----------	-----	---------	------	--------	------------------	----------	-------

The most important direct losses that Madagascar experienced from disaster events are those that occur after cyclones. Affected family dwellings (mostly made by local non-solid raw materials, woods, leaves, etc.) remain vulnerable to cyclonic wind [23]. A recent catastrophe risk modeling study estimates there is a 10% probability that damages will exceed \$240 million and a 5% probability that damages will exceed \$600 million [12]. The 73% loss from cyclone, 85% loss from flood and 65% loss from earthquakes originate all from the residential sectors. Tropical cyclones are by far the most significant risk, causing approximately 85 % of the annual average loss from all three perils. A 100-year return period tropical cyclone event would produce direct losses of \$810 million and require approximately \$190 million in emergency costs (Table 3) [13].

Between 19-23 January 2020, heavy rains in the northwestern part of Madagascar caused a big damage, 7 out of the 22 regions and 13 districts were severely affected. More than 126,000 people affected, infrastructure was severely damaged or destroyed [17]. On 17 February 2021 the National Office for Risk and Disaster Management (BNGRC) in Madagascar reported that 1 person has died around 1,400 people have been affected by recent heavy rainfall, floods and landslides across the regions of Alaotra-Mangoro, Analamanga, Melaky and Menabe. Over 200 homes have been damaged.

Table 3: Average annual loss and 100-year period loss [24]

Peril	Average Annual Loss		100 Year Return Period Loss	
	Total Direct Losses	Emergency Costs	Total Direct Losses	Emergency Costs
Earthquakes	\$1.3 million	\$200,000	\$15 million	\$2.3 million
Floods	\$13 million	\$3.1 million	\$120 million	\$27 million
Tropical Cyclones	\$87 million	\$20 million	\$810 million	\$190 million

Due to the impact of the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, the economic growth in 2020 is expected to slow from the forecast of 5.3 % to 0.17 %. COVID-19 pushed 1.38 million people into extreme poverty due to job losses in key manufacturing and service sectors, as well as the sudden loss of income for informal workers affected by lockdowns in major cities. The poverty rate (\$1.9/day) is estimated to rise to 77.4% in 2020, up from 74.3% in 2019 [19]. COVID-19 has exacerbated the vulnerabilities of communities for preventing and responding to disasters.

3. Best practices for disaster management

Madagascar has a large and active disaster risk management (DRM) community, consisting of government, donors and nongovernmental organizations [12]. Disaster risk management in Madagascar is the responsibility of the Minister of Interior. The Prime Minister Office is the entity that houses the National Office for Risk and

Disaster Management (BNGRC) and the Emergency Reduction and Management Agency (CPGU). These two state agencies deal with preparedness, response, relief and recovery after cyclones and other disaster events. While the CPGU is mandated to intervene both in disaster risk reduction and disaster management, the BNGRC focuses mainly on emergency management after a disaster though it is planning now disaster risk reduction activities [23]. At the local level, the BNGRC is supported through Disaster Management Committees that have been established by municipal decree for each area. Through the committee, members share experiences and are able to advise BNGRC to help improve the implementation plan of the national strategy on disaster and risk management [25]. BNGRC used a national contingency plan as a reference tool for disaster preparedness and response. The contingency plan is based on data collected from the representatives of actors or groups of actors involved in disaster risk reduction in Madagascar.

A key step taken by the Government of Madagascar is to include disaster risk reduction in the national development policy and the consideration of disaster risk reduction in all national poverty reduction programs [25]. One of the strategic areas of the country's 2016-2030 National Development Plan is the adoption of a strong DRM policy framework and a range of strategies for DRM and climate change adaptation which aim to strengthen the financial resilience to disasters.

Partnership is powering progress toward a resilient future in Madagascar. In the last few years, the Government of Madagascar has been able to transition from a post-disaster relief focus to the adoption of disaster risk management and climate change resilience strategies, building on important long-term engagement with several development partners. The Government of Madagascar has prioritized improving financial resilience to natural hazards and integrating disaster risk management and climate change considerations in its planning and strategy development processes [12].

4. Problems militating against best practices for managing disasters

Like any developing country, Madagascar does not have enough resources, both financial and human, to achieve disaster risk reduction. The national strategy on disaster risk management has been slow to evolve into a practical strategy at the community level. The BNGRC at the central level only rushes to remote areas whenever there is a disaster at the site [26]. In addition, the elements of the early warning system for droughts, cyclones and floods are the Meteo Malagasy, radios, televisions and social media. While for other hazards, the early warning system does not yet exist. Moreover, some infrastructures were not designed to withstand natural disasters such as cyclones and floods [8]. Severely damaged infrastructures are essentials for transports and social services sectors: roads, telecommunications, water supply, crop storage, health and education buildings. These situations are not only the results of extreme conditions but also of non-compliance with construction standards, particularly anticyclonic [20]. Another factor blocking the effectiveness of risk reduction is the lack of concern among the population. Some people sometimes ignore the risk they encountered due to the dependence on the aid that they obtained after the disaster. In another cases, poverty and environmental degradation increase the risks and vulnerabilities of its population because the capacity of the population to

have an appropriate living environment is low. Poor households have a low quality of housing and construction, therefore significant building vulnerabilities

Conclusion

Natural disasters pose a growing threat in the world, especially for developing countries like Madagascar, both in terms of frequency and damage. Cyclone, drought, flood, earthquake, epidemic and landslides are the common disasters in Madagascar. The most important losses from disaster events are those that occur after cyclones. Cyclones constitute less than 40 percent of recorded disasters, over two-thirds of mortality and 90 percent of the affected population can be attributed to this single hazard type.

Madagascar has made efforts regarding standards and structures in terms of disaster risk management but reinforcements and improvements are still needed to make this management more effective. Disaster management in Madagascar should no longer rely on the reaction to hazards, but clearly rely on preparedness for events that never happened. Planning for disaster preparedness should lead to development of measurable objectives and outcomes to strengthen readiness. Awareness and preparedness to face the calamity help to solve the magnitude of the problems so people must be well aware of the occurrence of disaster. It is recommended to establish a sustainable disaster risk management policy with financing plan and arrangements in advance to enable timely, effective and appropriate responses to specific potential hazardous events or emerging disaster situations that might threaten society or the environment. It is important that all dimensions of society take part in disaster management activities: from each member of the family to the various stakeholders and decision-makers at different levels. In the case of cyclones and floods, the communities must regularly carry out simulation exercises corresponding to the behaviors adopted according to the different warning phases. As well as the enforcement of building codes and regulations relating to land use, zoning and planning, for example encouraging the community to build houses and infrastructure that are resistant to disasters.

Aside from raising community consciousness about disaster risk reduction, it is critical to build best practices and lessons learned from past experience.

References

1. Hannah L, Dave R, Lowry PP, Andelman S, Andrianarisata M, Andriamaro L, et al. Climate change adaptation for conservation in Madagascar. *Biol Lett*. 2008;4(5):590–4.
2. Badji H, Senior U, Michele C, Programme U, Ousmane O, Yan UJ. Rapport sur l’Evaluation des Capacités en Matière de Réduction des Risques de Catastrophes à Madagascar. 2012;39.
3. UNFCCC. Madagascar ’ S Intended Nationally Determined Contribution. 2015;1–13.
4. USAID. Climate Risks in Urban and Urbanizing Geographies Madagascar. 2018;(March):26.
5. UNISDR. Global Assessment Report on Disaster Risk Reduction 2015a. 2015.
6. David E., Vera K. LS. Global climate risk index 2020 [Internet]. 2020. 1–28 p. Available from: <https://germanwatch.org/en/download/7170.pdf>
7. Rafalimanana A. Contribution to the prevention of cyclonic risks by using the wrf-arw model as a

- forecast means: case of cyclone Hellen March 2014 in the North West region of Madagascar. 2014.
8. ACF-International. Case Studies : Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation. ACF-International Rep. 2014;1–23.
 9. UNISDR. Risk and poverty in a changing climate. United Nations publications. 2009.
 10. Ratsimamanga A., Bettencourt S. The management of natural risks: towards reinforced and coordinated prevention. 2010;351–64.
 11. BNGRC. Madagascar’s Multi-Risk Contingency Plan. 2016;95.
 12. World Bank. Country Partnership Framework for the Republic of Madagascar for the Period of FY17-FY21. Ctry Partnersh Framew Repub Madagascar Period FY17-FY21. 2017;(114744):96.
 13. GFDRR-World Bank. Disaster Risk Profile: Madagascar [Internet]. 2017. Available from: <https://www.gfdr.org/sites/default/files/madagascar.pdf>
 14. Stephan N. The first months of COVID-19 in Madagascar. Infect Genet Evol [Internet]. 2020;85(July). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meegid.2020.104506>
 15. OCHA. EMERGENCY APPEAL FOR COVID-19 MADAGASCAR overview. 2020;(July):30.
 16. Michelle V. E., Andres G., Rado J.L., John M., Drake, Benjamin A., Elinambinina R., Calistus N., Benjamin R., Matthew H. JR. Reconciling model predictions with low reported cases of COVID-19 in Sub-Saharan Africa: Insights from Madagascar. medRxiv. 2020;13.
 17. UNICEF. Madagascar Country Office. 2020;(June):1–9.
 18. Johns Hopkins University Coronavirus Resource Center. Coronavirus Cases - Madagascar. 2021;1–13.
 19. World Bank. Madagascar Economic Update: Setting a course for recovery, COVID-19. Mod Plast. 2020;78(10):32.
 20. CPGU, BNGRC, PNUD. Madagascar: National disaster risk management strategy 2016-2030. 2016;32. Available from: <http://extwprlegs1.fao.org/docs/pdf/mad166143.pdf>
 21. Ramasiarinoro V. J., Andrianaivo L. RE. Landslides and associated mass movements events in the eastern part of Madagascar : risk assessment , land use planning , mitigation measures and further strategies. Madamines. 2012;4:28–41.
 22. EM-DAT C/ Ucl. Disaster Madagascar. 2021;
 23. UNISDR. UNISDR Working Papers on Public and Financing Strategy for Disaster Risk Reduction: Review of Madagascar. 2015;(February). Available from: [http://www.wcdr.org/wcdr-data/uploads/871/2.UNISDR Working Papers on Public Investment Planning and Financing Strategy for DRR-Review of Madagascar.pdf](http://www.wcdr.org/wcdr-data/uploads/871/2.UNISDR%20Working%20Papers%20on%20Public%20Investment%20Planning%20and%20Financing%20Strategy%20for%20DRR-Review%20of%20Madagascar.pdf)
 24. GFDRR WB. Disaster Risk Profile Madagascar. 2017;
 25. BNGRC U. Madagascar: Cyclone Enawo. 2017;(1):9–10.
 26. Randriamilamana G. Reflection on the recurrent flooding of the city of Toliara. 2015;78.

RAKOTOARIMANANA Zy Misa Harivelo
Disaster Management Department
Universitas Airlangga, Indonesia

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.

